

THE IMPORTANCE OF DIDACTIC GAMES IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

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Abstract: The paper highlights the importance of didactic games in strengthening students' knowledge, broadening their understanding, and developing their creative abilities. It explores techniques and methods to engage preschoolers in activities that pique their interest. Language is a critical skill for preschoolers, and it is a prerequisite for quality education in the classroom and university. The study aims to find innovative ways to engage preschoolers in learning.

Keywords: Didactic Game; Activity; Education; Quality of Teaching; Formative Values.

1. INTRODUCTION

This paper emphasizes the role of the didactic game—a particular kind of exercise—in helping the didactic framework to strengthen, clarify, and even validate students' knowledge, broaden the field of knowledge, and foster and develop their creative abilities. One of the most critical abilities that a preschooler learns is language. It is also a prerequisite for receiving a quality education in the classroom and, eventually, at a university.

Semantic, grammatical, lexical, and phonetic evolution are all aspects of language development. Preschoolers are renowned to be great conversationalists; in addition to being voracious questioners, they also like sharing a great deal of information. This function is very helpful to parents and teachers when it comes to helping children build their vocabulary and communication abilities.

The impacts of mothers reading to their children throughout the first three years of their lives were examined in a recent study by Raikes H., Pan B.A., Luze G., Tamis-LeMonda, C.S., Brooks-Gunn, J., Constantine, J., Tarullo, L.B., Raikes, H.A., & Rodriguez, E.T. (2006). It is recommended that parents read stories to their kids in order to support linguistic and cognitive development. In an evaluation study, mothers and kids took part in Early Head Start, a government program that serves 62,000 low-income families across 7,000 locations in the United States. Early Head Start provides services to enhance parenting abilities and child development in homes or at service centers. Interviews were conducted with over 1,100 women who were 14, 24, and 36 months old. A portion of them took part in the Early Head Start initiative, whereas others took part in the Early Head Start program. We questioned mothers on how often they read stories to their kids. Concerns and resources within the family have also been brought up. Standard assessments of children's vocabulary and cognitive capacities were conducted by knowledgeable researchers. When the child reached the age of 14, nearly half of the moms reported reading to them every day, and the proportion of mothers increased as the child grew older. The child's cognitive and verbal outcomes at the same age and later in life were correlated with how often they read.

In general, children who have their mothers read to them regularly throughout their first two years of life develop a greater vocabulary and cognitive abilities. This means that by the time children reach the age of three, when they begin to show interest in pre-reading activities, the children who have had their mothers read to them regularly have substantially higher cognitive and language scores.

The most significant finding was that the mother's reading habits had an impact on the child's language through a "snowball" effect, demonstrating that early reading exposure improves speech abilities, which in turn helps children learn to read and use vocabulary. To put it another way, infants who were exposed to reading at a young age started talking earlier and exhibited a curiosity about books, which led to an increase in reading interest and the subsequent development

of cognitive and vocabulary skills. The game consists of a series of tasks and activities that aim to further the child's intellectual, technical, moral, and physical development in addition to promoting relaxation, happiness, and good mood.

As a result, when the game is incorporated into the teaching process, it takes on important psychopedagogical roles that guarantee children's active engagement in activities and heighten their curiosity about the subject matter. Integrated activities require a particular level of integration between various knowledge domains and methodologies, in addition to the usage of a common language that facilitates conceptual and methodological exchanges. Transferring methods from one discipline to another, with varying degrees of commitment and completion, is another aspect of integrated activity.

Integration can also take the form of linking data unique to certain domains and breaking down barriers between them by exchanging techniques, expertise, and resources. The relationship between knowledge related to various activity categories and children's ability to apply knowledge in the real world is greatly aided by this correlation; knowledge from one domain can be transferred to another and one discipline can help another be better mastered. Language instruction has a significant role in a child's readiness for school, since it significantly impacts the growth of all psychological processes as well as the child's personality.

Preschool education is the earliest stage of education and is designed with a systematic vision in mind. It follows a structure, follows a process, and produces a particular product. Early childhood education is defined as providing special conditions for a child's complete development while honoring their unique age and developmental stage. It covers the period from birth to age eight. Early education is based on the theory that a kid's personality develops at a young age and that, in order for the child to succeed academically, all the variables with which it interacts—family, teachers, and the community—must be trained. Insufficient care,

affection, and attention during a child's early years can result in a learning disability that could jeopardize the child's future growth and academic prospects.

A child's sense of self emerges and their identity is formed during their first two years of life. For him to see how he thinks and how he believes others should collaborate with him for the first time is crucial in this regard. Early education considers a few crucial concepts in a child's personality development:

- Every child is different and has needs that are personal to them.
- Education never ends; it starts in the earliest stages of life and continues indefinitely.
- Engaging in active connection with an adult is defining, and every act of care is an instructional method.
- A child's growth is influenced by the opportunities provided by their regular schedule.
- Young toddlers learn through experimentation and engagement in game environments.

The toddler encounters a novel situation when he first starts kindergarten. Educational ideas have benefited greatly from the contributions of renowned psychologist Jean Piaget. The four phases that he listed are:

- Sensorimotor development stage (birth to two years): Physical interactions and experiences form the basis of an infant's understanding of the world.
- Preoperative period (2–7 years): During this time, a child's use of symbols boosts their intelligence, their memory and reasoning skills are closely linked to language use, and their thinking is egocentric and irreversible.
- The Operational Concrete Stage (7–12 years): During this stage, a child's intelligence grows and they exhibit a logical and methodical use of symbols in close relationship to tangible objects. Their thinking is operational, reversible, and less egocentric.
- Status of Formal Operations (more than 12 years) - Thinking is psycho-behavioural, a fundamental trait that will significantly impact the child's degree of

adaptation and integration in the later stages of his evolution and development. - Intelligence is felt through the application of logic of symbols, in close connection with abstract notions.

Early childhood is a time of exploration; a youngster learns via games that there is a fascinating world out there and wants to learn more about it. The game is a vital activity that is initially played alone, then parallels other people's games and is marked by impulsivity and discontinuity. At this age, the child avoids social situations, is even scared of them, and has periods of intense uncertainty. However, when they develop certain behaviors along the road, the child comes to trust him, and he plays the game every day. He overcomes his need for movement, his curiosity, and even his phobias through the game.

The exercises' rich information is made accessible through language and changes as a result of learning abilities that will be useful to an individual's later stages of development. The didactic game is the most complex type of play in early childhood education and has a significant formative impact on young children. One of the most crucial pre-school education requirements, the correct acquisition of the Romanian language, is realized through the didactic game as a fundamental activity in the development of preschool speech. This condition determines the development of thinking and other psychological and intellectual processes. A youngster who can accurately pronounce words, who is motivated to find vocabulary enrichment solutions, who gains self-confidence and shows interest in activities, will all benefit from these skills.

2. FUNCTIONS OF THE GAME

Psychologists have demonstrated that play is crucial to a child's development. The concept of game functions is also involved in other classifications. There are key and supporting features in the game. The primary purpose of the game is to help the player identify and define his personality. Consequently, "a substitute for serious work" would be the play that follows Claparède. There are two reasons why everyone must utilize the game.

• Because of circumstances that prevent him from engaging in a significant task that fulfills his desire; or • Because of his limited development, which prevents him from performing serious labor. Therefore, the barriers may be internal (moral censoring) or external (wrong surroundings). The following functions are most frequently seen in the literature:

• **COGNITIVE FUNCTION** is a knowledge-based function. The child's favorite pastime in kindergarten is playing the game, which he is always encouraged to play. This innate drive to play is what forms the framework for how the educational process is organized.

• Assimilation of social and physical realities results in **ADAPTIVE FUNCTION**. The preschool masterfully adapts through the game to the physical and social environment, making it easier to deal with the pressures of everyday life and the outside world.

• **FORMATIVE FUNCTION** is **ESSENTIAL**, as emphasized by educators such as **FROBEL** and refined by contemporary teaching. The child's brain activity is stimulated by workout games, which is how it is achieved. Children use their analytical skills to consider potential solutions to the real-world challenges the game presents in order to keep playing. The game stimulates the child's imagination and creative thinking. Children can deal with real-life issues by using their imaginative creativity.

• A child's constant high propensity to accommodate others while also assimilating their relationships with those around them is a hallmark of socialization. This trait is particularly noticeable in rule play and entails the youngster accepting rules both inside and outside of the classroom, but once it is earned, it becomes a benefit. Youngsters can experiment, discover, and pick up new skills. An essential component of socialization through play is the child's inclination to protect their individuality as well as their desire to fit in with society.

• The term "**PSYCHIC RELEVANCE FUNCTION**" describes how a youngster experiences life and how they translate their emotions and worries. The

game, the way the youngster selects their material resources, the subject, and their gaming companions all contribute to these unique, vivid experiences of the child. Teachers and parents are able to identify any disruptions in the child's growth. A child's character can be shaped by a variety of factors, including their degree of intellectual development, their life experiences, and the adult role model. The youngster assumes control of his surroundings and the framework of his life.

- **EDUCATIONAL FUNCTION:** This describes how the game helps with cognitive function enhancement, internal motivation engagement, and skill development. Here, we're talking about the game's activities that support a child's physical and mental growth while also giving them the skills and abilities necessary for intellectual work and facilitating their smooth transition into a new social setting. We can identify the balance and healing functions of the didactic game as its secondary roles.

3. GAME CLASSIFICATION

The fundamental kindergarten exercise is a game. As I've already mentioned, the youngster attempts to learn about the outside world through the game, which is regarded as a pre-learning activity. The youngster learns about his environment, satisfies his desire for movement and comprehension, develops self-confidence, and forms his personality by interacting with the things and people in it. Since enjoyment, motivation, and satisfaction are invariably accompanied by a sense of fulfillment and delight, the game must provide these feelings.

Youngsters are drawn to the novelty of anything new, therefore the game is entwined with wonder and curiosity. Each of these fosters their curiosity and encourages them to explore. The development of curiosity pushes kids to solve problems, try new things, ask questions, observe, and explore—all of which give situations involving them a joyful quality. While it is more prevalent in motion games, the game also allows for some degree of movement. Youngsters are free to select their own partners, play for as long as they like, share roles, and alter the rules whenever they please.

Preschool educators have been fascinated with the classification of games. "By ordering their classification according to the function they fulfil, Edgar Claparède classifies the games into two major categories: games that perform general functions and games that perform special functions." (Tomşa, 2005). Piaget puts the games in the following categories after classifying them based on evolutionary principles:

- Exercise games; Symbolic games; Rules Games; Construction games

4. THE EDUCATIONAL GAME'S IMPACT ON A CHILD'S INTELLECTUAL GROWTH

The game helps preschoolers' minds grow in two ways: by fostering their imagination and by imparting new knowledge. Both children and adults engage in imaginative play, with the environment supporting the expression and growth of their imagination. "The game's involuntary memory serves merely as a prelude to the game's voluntary learning of its rules. Thinking processes are involved in generalization and classification as didactic game requirements, and they are simpler to complete when driven by the requirements game. The development of language is essential to a child's growth since it serves social and regulatory purposes and is intimately tied to thought processes. Voiculescu (2001). The goal of the game, particularly the didactic version, is to teach basic vocabulary, correct and enhance pronunciation, and learn specific nouns that relate to nearby objects or phenomena. Throughout the child's development, the teacher must stay by his side, accompany him, and provide him with covert guidance. It serves as the child's primary source of stimulation, constant correction, and knowledge expansion. In addition, the teacher fosters the child's creativity and helps him communicate his thoughts, feelings, and desires. The teacher recognizes his uniqueness while yet verbally pushing him to grow.

5. THE ROLE THAT THE GAME PLAYS IN A CHILD'S MORAL DEVELOPMENT

The youngster cannot choose the reference values or discriminate between good and evil when they are preschool age. Positive values must shape the child's development, and bad values must be eradicated entirely. In actuality, this is the core of moral instruction. The family serves as the child's major environment for moral instruction up until the time of kindergarten entry, as well as throughout school. The teacher can play the desiderata of the pre-school moral education through the game, which refers to a number of general objectives connected to the social area - the attitude, the affective area, and the cognitive area. The teacher can play a significant role in inspiring moral education.

The main moral ideals can be used by the child in a broad context through exercise games, role-playing games, and rules games. An adult should assess preschool purchases based on behavior.

Children's relationships benefit greatly from the game since they are viewed as desirable, accepted, and correctly expressing themselves while resisting bad feelings. It gives kids an external incentive to practice self-control, self-mastery, tenacity, honesty, competition, and fair play. It also helps them develop certain behavioral skills and standards. Playful fiction can be used as an instructional medium and framework by stimulating through play.

It is a difficult duty for educators to help children develop morally. She needs to teach the youngster how to resolve the tension between her own desires and the game's rules. It is the finest activity for developing self-regulation since the youngster will internalize the educator's external regulation and eventually become independent. In due course, the preschool will have some of the models she previously presented, negating the need for the educator's stimulus; in the meantime, the kid will adapt her behavior based on feedback from her playmates. The greatest motivation to keep playing this game is the understanding, validation, and fulfillment of being accepted as a partner by others.

6. THE USE OF TOYS IN PRESCHOOL GAMES AND THEIR FORMATIVE VALUES IN A CHILD'S DEVELOPMENT

For the young infant, the toy is crucial. It defines the nature of the game and the child's emotional journey. The toy has a variety of formative meanings. Thinking skills such as analysis, synthesis, comparison, and generalization are acquired through puzzle games, demountable toys, doll houses, and toy kitchens. The shifting dolls, accessory machines, and thematic games (farm, firefighter, shop, etc.) all foster creativity and imagination. Children's ability to understand form and spatial relationships is enhanced by manipulating certain toys (such as swings, illustrated cubes, rising glasses, puzzles, etc.). Talking and constant communication with their favorite toys (musical toys, narrative books, interactive dolls, etc.) helps children acquire a great deal of language. The baby's toy will be its most prized possession because it is priceless and plays a significant part in its development. The youngster gains confidence and self-assurance from it, the character of the adult of tomorrow.

The word "didactic" used to describe the game highlights the instructive and educational nature of the activity, which is essential to it and is made concrete by the information, common sense, and mental exercises it calls for. The didactic game provides an instructive and formative element to the educational process, regardless of the child's age.

Since this type of play trains the child to stimulate and practice speech in the suggested direction inside each game without understanding this effort, teaching plays a specific function in the development of preschoolers' speech. Compared to other kindergarten activities, didactic games are more appealing and successful since every child in the group puts out the same amount of mental and expressive effort.

References / Список литературы

1. Bondarenko A.K. Didactic games in kindergarten; 2nd edition, revised. Moscow. Enlightenment, 1991. P. 210.

2. Veraksa N.E. "From birth to school": The main educational program of preschool, education / under the editorship of Veraksa N.E., T.S. Komarova, M.A. Vasilyeva; 3rd ed. Moscow, 2016. P. 386
3. Sodikova Sh. Preschool pedagogy. - Т., "Tafakkur bo'stoni", 1992.
4. Norkuziyev D. The initial influence of life strategy on the formation of the teenager // European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences, UK Volume 6, number 2, 2018 ISSN 2056-5852; – P. 91-94.
4. Hasanboeva O.U. and others. Pedagogy of preschool education. Т.: Science. 2006.
5. Воспитание и обучение детей шестого года жизни. / Под ред. Л.А.Парамоновой, О.С. Ушаковой. М.: Просвещение, 1987.
6. Истоки: Примерная основная общеобразовательная программа дошкольного образования. – 4-е изд., перераб. и доп./ Под ред. Л.А. Парамоновой. М.: ТЦ Сфера, 2001. 320 с.
7. Катаева А.А., Стребелева Е.А. Дидактические игры и упражнения. М.: БУК-МАСТЕР, 1993
8. Norkuziyev D. The problems of life strategies typologization // Proceedings of International Multidisciplinary Scientific-Remote Online Conference on Innovative Solutions and Advanced Experiments Samarkand Regional Center for Retraining and Advanced Training of Public Education Staff Samarkand, Uzbekistan Journal. June 18th & 19th, 2020. – P. 864-866